

Research article

Effect of substrate size reduction and periodic nutrient supplementation on biological wood oxidation

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ABSTRACT

Biological wood oxidation (BWO) is a composting heat recovery system tailored for woody lignocellulose valorization, with the potential to generate sustainable and low-temperature heat. This study investigated the effects of feedstock particle sizing and periodic nutrient supplementation (PNS) on microbial activity and wood decomposition during BWO. Birch wood was processed into sawdust (<5 mm) and cubes of various diameters (5, 10, and 15 mm), incubated in batch-mode BWO reactors for 88 days, and periodically supplemented with a nutrient medium. Sawdust-BWO outperformed cubes-BWO and demonstrated greater sensitivity to PNS, exhibiting in total 207% higher cumulative oxygen consumption, 50%~ higher nitrogen utilization efficiency, 217% higher wood dry matter (DM) loss, and 101% higher total carbohydrates removal. The use of human urine as a nutrient source, combined with sawdust and PNS, further enhanced the BWO performance and resulted in an unprecedented 34.2% DM loss and 45.5% total carbohydrate removal over a 60-day incubation period. As revealed by an overall energy balance analysis, the process of grinding wood cubes into sawdust consumes around 55–72 kWh/t DM of additional electricity but results in a potentially 10-fold increase in heat output (680.6–719.5 kWh/t DM). Hence, combining fine grinding of wood with PNS emerges as an effective and energy-efficient strategy to elevate the performance and heat generation potential of BWO.

1. Introduction

Lignocellulose, the principal polymer derived from plant biomass, is abundantly available as by-product in global agricultural and forestry sectors. Recycling lignocellulosic biomass for energy production is a crucial alternative to fossil fuels (Mujtaba et al., 2023). Bioenergy can be produced from lignocellulose via (1) thermal conversion, i.e. combustion, (2) thermochemical conversions, i.e. pyrolysis and gasification, and (3) biological conversions, aided by bioagents and/or enzymes (Haq et al., 2021). While each conversion route has its limitations and advantages, biological approaches offer several general advantages over thermal and thermochemical methods, including: (i) higher conversion efficiency and selectivity due to the action of biocatalysts (Haq et al., 2021); (ii) milder operational conditions, which lower operational costs and reduce risks associated with explosions and noise pollution (Marulanda et al., 2019); (iii) reduced formation of recalcitrant and hard-to-degrade byproducts (Okolie et al., 2022); and (iv) particular suitability for feedstocks with high moisture content (Okolie et al.,

2022).

The rate and efficiency of biological lignocellulosic conversions are greatly influenced by the characteristics of substrate, which can vary significantly across different feedstocks. Broadly speaking, lignocellulose can be categorized into woody and non-woody (agricultural) lignocellulose. While non-woody lignocellulose can be transformed into various biofuels (e.g. ethanol, methane, and biogas) with relatively high efficiency (Ji et al., 2022; Passoth and Sandgren, 2019), woody lignocellulose, comprising over 80% of biomass energy feedstock (Menon and Rao, 2012), is generally a difficult substrate for efficient biofuel conversions due to its larger physical size, stronger structural density, higher lignin content, and consequently greater resistance to microbial and enzymatic degradation (Liu, 2010; Zhu and Pan, 2010). An alternative approach to harness energy from lignocellulose is compost heat recovery systems (CHRS), wherein meso-thermophilic microbes aerobically degrade lignocellulose (often in mix with animal manure) to produce recoverable low-temperature heat and humus-rich soil amendments (Fan et al., 2021; Malesani et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2017).

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For the application of CHRS, woody lignocellulose has several potential advantages over non-woody lignocellulose: (i) its structural strength creates interparticle voids for effective air, water, and heat transfer in large-scale composting piles (Iqbal et al., 2010; Pivato et al., 2024); (ii) it can be sourced from marginal lands or areas unsuitable for traditional agriculture, avoiding competition with food crops for arable land (Menon and Rao, 2012); (iii) its availability is less affected by seasonal changes and thus more reliable for continuous industrial operations (Liu et al., 2006).

The specific process of using wood as the sole substrate for CHRS has been referred to as biological wood oxidation (BWO) (Fan et al., 2020a, 2020b). Conceptually, BWO is tailored for low-value forestry residues that cannot be repurposed for higher-priority applications like construction and materials (Knauf, 2015), and for regions with limited access to animal manure or strict regulations on its use in composting (Viaene et al., 2016). In this sense, BWO diverges from conventional lignocellulosic composting in terms of substrate composition (exclusively woody biomass, without manure or slurry), dominant microbiome (fungi instead of bacteria, as fungi are more adept at wood degradation) (Embacher et al., 2023), operational temperatures (around 40 °C, considered optimal for thermophilic fungi) (Ryckeboer, J. et al., 2003), and nitrogen levels (significantly lower than in conventional composting to promote fungal activities) (Fan et al., 2020b). Still, the major technological hurdle of BWO is its slow reaction rates, primarily associated with the inherent recalcitrance of and limited availability of nutrients in woody lignocellulose. Substrate size reduction (SSR), the mechanical processing of lignocellulosic biomass into smaller fragments, is a fundamental pretreatment in many lignocellulose bioconversions. In practice, SSR often needs to be fine-tuned for different processes, as it can have dual effects on the microbial lignocellulosic conversion. On one hand, mechanical SSR can improve the biodegradability of lignocellulosic materials by: (i) decreasing the degree of depolymerization and crystallinity through disruption of the original ordered lignocellulosic structure (Csiszar et al., 2021), (ii) increasing the total accessible specific surface area for enzymatic attack (Vidal et al., 2011), and (iii) increasing the pore size of particles and the water holding capacity for improved mass transfer during hydrolytic reactions (Barakat et al., 2013). On the other hand, excessively small particle sizes can impede oxygen diffusion and lower the efficiency of bioconversion (Mishra and Yadav, 2022), and mechanical wood SSR demands additional energy investment (Walther et al., 2017). In conventional composts containing mixed waste streams, particle sizes of woody lignocellulose can range from 5 mm to 30 mm (Reyes-Torres et al., 2018), with 10–15 mm often reported as optimal for achieving high compost quality (Mishra and Yadav, 2022; Zhang and Sun, 2014). Previous BWO studies employed also 10–15 mm substrate size (Fan et al., 2020a, 2020b). It thus remains unknown whether reducing substrate size further (i.e., below 5 mm) could improve wood degradation in the context of BWO, and what the optimal sizing for BWO could be.

Besides the modification of woody lignocellulose itself, SSR may also influence the nutrient availability for BWO microbes. Since BWO features a fungi-dominating solid-state process with a relatively low water content, nutrients in the system mainly diffuse through the aqueous phase and are accessed by microorganisms growing on the wood particles (Gervais and Molin, 2003). Consequently, the water-holding capacity of the substrate pile becomes critical, which can be greatly influenced by the size, structure, and specific surface area of the wood particles. In previous studies, we have demonstrated the recycling of nitrogen-rich human urine to enhance BWO and the importance of nutrient re-supplementation for efficient long-running BWO (Fan et al., 2020a). Given that initially added nitrogen was consumed fairly quickly within the first 2–3 weeks, we hypothesized that a periodic nutrient supplementation (PNS) regime could be beneficial or even necessary for sustaining BWO operations, and its effectiveness is likely to be positively influenced by the particle size of wood.

Accordingly, the primary aim of this study was to improve the

performance of BWO by investigating the synergistic effects of SSR and PNS on various BWO performance parameters, including microbial oxygen consumption, nitrogen uptake, removal of lignocellulosic carbohydrates, and dry mass (DM) loss of wood. Employing the optimal particle size obtained, we conducted a secondary experiment comparing the efficacy of human urine and synthetic medium to explore the further enhancement of BWO. Due to the limited scale of the setup, directly measuring the heat production potential was not feasible. Instead, we estimated it based on the oxygen consumption, a method commonly adopted in the literature (Fan et al., 2021). The estimated heat production potential was used to evaluate the energy efficacy of SSR in enhancing BWO within a simplified upscaled BWO scenario.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Wood material

The wood species used in this study was silver birch (*Betula pendula*), one of the most important commercial tree species and sources of fuelwood in northern Europe (Manzone and Spinelli, 2014). Birch wood beams were purchased from a local supplier with basic characteristics listed in Table 1. Wood beams were either processed into cubes with diameters of 5, 10, and 15 mm by a panel saw (K700, Felder, Austria) and a thicknesser (343.190, INCA, Switzerland), or ground by a knife mill (Netzsch, Germany) and sieved into sawdust. The four groups of processed wood are referred to as WC5, WC10 and WC15 for 5-, 10-, and 15-mm wood cubes and SD for sawdust. The dimensional error of wood cubes, measured using a digital caliper (150 mm, Format, Germany), remained within ± 0.5 mm. The sawdust particles, with an average length of 5.2 mm and a cross-sectional diameter ranging from 0.8 to 1.0 mm, were viewed and measured under a NIKON Eclipse 400 microscope equipped with a Nikon CCD camera (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan). All wood materials were oven-dried at 105 °C overnight and stored at -20 °C until use.

2.2. Inoculum

BWO microorganisms sampled from a garden waste compost pile were cultivated on wood chips at 40 °C for more than 6 months, with a regular supply of air, nutrients, and fresh wood chips. To prepare the inoculum, 20 g of well-colonized wood chips were soaked in 150 mL of demineralized water, vortexed for 1 min, and then filtered using Whatman GF/B filter papers (1 μ m pore size) to remove solid impurities (Fan et al., 2020a). The filtrate, with an optical density of around 0.1 at 600 nm, was used as the inoculant.

Table 1
Characteristics of untreated wood materials.

Properties	Birch wood	Replicate
Heating value (HV, MJ/kg) ^a	18.36	\
Density (kg/m ³) ^b	570 \pm 35	10
Ash content (%) ^c	0.42 \pm 0.04	3
Water absorption (v/v, %) ^d	79.6 \pm 2.3	3
Glucan (% w/w) ^e	32.4 \pm 0.9	2
Glucuronarabinoxylan (GAX, % w/w) ^e	20.1 \pm 0.02	2
Lignin (% w/w) ^f	32.3 \pm 0.3	2

Note.

^a Derived from Abdesshahian et al. (2021) (Abdesshahian et al., 2021).

^b Calculated by dividing the dry mass of wood cubes by their corresponding volumes obtained from dimensional measurements.

^c Determined according to ISO 18122:2022 (2022).

^d Based on the weight change of wood before and after moisture saturation.

^e Based on constituent monosaccharide analysis after sulfuric acid hydrolysis as detailed below.

^f Based on quantitative ¹³C-IS pyrolysis-GC-MS, employing ¹³C willow lignin as internal standard (van Erven et al., 2019).

2.2.1. Nutrient supplementation

Two nutrient solutions were used in this study: synthetic medium (SM) and human urine (HU), with their characteristics listed in Table 2. The amount of both nutrient solutions supplemented in a single dose was 0.2 mL per gram of dry mass (DM) wood, corresponding to a nitrogen level of approximately 0.11% (w/w) (Fan et al., 2020a). SM contains essential elements for wood-decaying fungi (Martani et al., 2017) and bacteria (Deschamps et al., 1980), with a total nitrogen concentration (supplied by ammonium sulfate) comparable to that in HU. Since urea hydrolysis can increase the buffer capacity of HU, additional phosphate salts were incorporated into SM, providing a buffering capacity of around 50 mM (Udert et al., 2006). The formula for SM is (in g/L, unless specified): $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 25; K_2SO_4 , 7; KH_2PO_4 , 5; Na_2HPO_4 , 84.5; MgSO_4 , 2; CaCl_2 , 1; trace element solution, 1 mL. The trace element solution consisted of (g/L): $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 6; $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1; $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.2; $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.2. HU sample was provided by a healthy adult male and was carefully preserved in a tightly sealed, sterile container at 4 °C until its use. The characteristics of HU are aligned with the composition ranges observed in healthy human urine samples (Sarigul et al., 2019) and fresh urine samples collected from a substantial cohort of individuals (Simha et al., 2023). Chemical oxygen demand (COD), total nitrogen (TN), ammonium nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$), nitrate nitrogen ($\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$), and nitrite nitrogen ($\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N}$) were analyzed in duplicates spectrophotometrically using Hach-Lange test kits (Hach-Lange, Germany) after proper dilution. ICP-OES measurements were performed with an Optima Avio 500 optical emission spectrometer (PerkinElmer, USA) to analyze the elements Na, K, Ca, Mg, and P.

2.3. Experimental design

BWO was performed in air-tight glass bottles (650 mL, Schott, Germany) and operated in an incubator (Elbanton, Netherlands) at 40 °C (Fan et al., 2020a, 2020b). The setup is schematically shown in Fig. S1. The first experiment investigated the synergistic effect of particle size and PNS on BWO using SM. Table 3 summarizes the quantities of wood materials, the initial volumes of the inoculant, nutrient solution, and demineralized water introduced to various treatment groups.

Before inoculation, all wood materials were saturated with a mixture of nutrient solution and demineralized water (in a volume ratio of 1:9) to ensure sufficient moisture absorption. The total moisture content in the system was $220 \pm 5\%$ of DM wood (Fan et al., 2020a). Images of the actual reactors after loading are shown in Fig. 1.

Nutrient supplementation involves adding the same amount of nutrient solution as initially introduced to the bottles, followed by manually stirring the substrate to facilitate the nutrient distribution among particles. The residual total dissolved nitrogen (TDN, % of the initial) in the system was analyzed to indicate nutrient availability, and nutrient supplementation was performed once the residual TDN fell below 10%. The fastest-depleting group consumed its TDN within 14 days, leading to PNS starting on day 18 (after a 4-day delay for TDN analysis) and recur every 14 days. All four groups received nutrient

Table 2
Characteristics of two nutrient solutions used in this study.

Parameter (mg/L, except for pH)	Synthetic medium (SM)	Human urine (HU)
COD	86 ± 10	3722 ± 44
TN	5250	5340 ± 26
$\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$	5250	328 ± 13
$\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$	0	91 ± 5
$\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N}$	0	0.85 ± 0.08
Na	21,365.2	2199.6
K	4566.2	725.3
Ca	360.4	50.0
Mg	97.4	32.6
P	751.8	322.8
pH	7.65	5.90

solution simultaneously to ensure comparable total nutrient addition, despite the variations in the values of residual TDN among groups. The experimental duration spanned 88 days, involving five rounds of PNS. Intermittent samplings were conducted on each PNS day by selecting and terminating one replicate close to the median value. Subsequent statistical analysis was performed exclusively on the remaining replicates. Each treatment group initially comprised eight replicates, with three remaining at the end of the experiment.

In the second experiment, sawdust was selected as the form of substrate to assess (1) the efficacy of BWO with and without PNS and (2) the effectiveness of HU versus SM. The experiment comprised three treatment groups: SD-HU, SD-HU-PNS, and SD-SM-PNS, all were equipped with the same initial contents as specified for the SD group in Table 3. Notably, PNS was stopped after three recurrences, resulting in a total experimental duration of 60 days. There were a total of six replicates for treatments SD-HU-PNS and SD-SM-PNS, with three remaining on day 60. Due to limited experimental capacity, the SD-HU group had only three replicates and all were sampled on day 60.

2.4. Measurement of oxygen concentration

The oxygen concentration ($[\text{O}_2]$) inside the bottles was measured daily by Fibox 4 trace and Sensor Spot SP-Pst 3 (PreSens, Germany) and used for calculating the cumulative oxygen consumption on the day i (CO_2 , in mol/kg DM) and oxygen consumption rate (OCR_i , in mol/kg DM/d). The procedures of $[\text{O}_2]$ measurement and air refreshing were described in previous work (Fan et al., 2020a).

2.5. Measurement of residual total dissolved nitrogen (TDN)

The analysis for residual TDN followed the procedure established in previous work (Fan et al., 2020a). In brief, the BWO residue underwent a 3-day water extraction at 4 °C with minimal air contact. During the extraction, microbial activity was halted by the addition of 1% (w/w) NaN_3 , and the enzyme-catalyzed degradation of soluble TDN and other organic compounds was supposed to be minor due to low temperature and limited oxygen availability (Shukla et al., 2016). The water extracts were filtered through 0.45 μm membrane filters to remove insoluble material. The remaining nitrogen content in the filtrate was considered TDN and quantified spectrophotometrically using Total Nitrogen cuvette tests (LANTON LCK338, Hach-Lange, Germany) as described (Fan et al., 2020a). Standard deviations were calculated based on technical duplicates for each intermittent sample and on three biological replicates for the final sampling.

2.6. Determination of dry mass loss of wood

The residue after water extraction was dried at 105 °C for 72 h. DM loss was calculated from the initial and final weights:

$$\text{DM loss (\%)} = \frac{\text{initial dry weight} - \text{final dry weight}}{\text{initial dry weight}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.7. Constituent monosaccharide analysis

Dried wood samples were first crushed into sawdust with a diameter of less than 3 mm (Netzsch, Germany), then planetary ball milled for 45 min at 200 rpm (Pulverisette-5, Fritsch GmbH, Germany). Milling beakers made of sintered corundum (99.7% Al_2O_3) had a volume of 500 mL and were equipped with sintered corundum balls (30 mm diameter), all purchased from Fritsch GmbH, Germany. Duplicates of the powdered samples were subjected to two-stage sulfuric acid hydrolysis followed by monosaccharide content analysis to determine the lignocellulosic carbohydrates as previously described (van Erven et al., 2023). Anhydroglucose served as the measure for cellulose content, and the sum of anhydroglucuronic acid, anhydroarabinose, and anhydroxylose served

Fig. 1. BWO reactors loaded with differently sized wood particles and nutrient solution. In SD (sawdust), moisture is evenly distributed among solid particles, resembling a solid-state fermentation process. In WC5, WC10, and WC15 (wood cubes with 5, 10, 15 mm diameter), a distinct gas-water interface was observed, with certain part of wood cubes submerged and the rest exposed directly to air.

Table 3
Contents of BWO reactors for the investigation of SSR coupled with PNS.

	Substrate size	No. of cubes	DM (g)	Inoculant (mL)	Nutrient solution (mL)	Demi-water (mL)
SD	<5 mm	\	6.50 ± 0.01	1.30	1.30	11.7
WC5	5 mm	3	6.76 ± 0.04	1.35	1.35	12.2
WC10	10 mm	10	6.28 ± 0.03	1.25	1.25	11.3
WC15	15 mm	80	6.16 ± 0.08	1.24	1.24	11.1

as the measure for glucuronoarabinoxylan (GAX) content.

2.8. Energy evaluation of BWO

For the evaluation of energy performance, a larger-scale BWO reactor was conceptualized as a vertically oriented solid cylinder operated within a controlled environment. The reactor was designed to provide a space for 1000 kg of dry matter (DM) wood, leaving 50% of the volume as a headspace. The diameter and height of the reactor were calculated from the total volume. The characteristics of the conceptual BWO are outlined in Table S1.

To assess the heat generation potential of BWO under different treatment conditions, the theoretical heat generation (Q_{bio}), convective heat losses, conductive heat losses, and useful heat output (Q_A) were calculated following the procedure specified in supplementary materials, using calculation parameters listed in Table S2. Two key indicators were introduced to evaluate the energy efficiency of BWO: thermal

efficiency (TE), defined as the ratio of theoretical heat generation to the total heat potential of feedstock, and specific energy consumption (SEC) associated with SSR, defined as the energy needed for wood processing divided by useful heat output.

TE was expressed as:

$$TE = \frac{Q_{bio}}{HV \cdot m_{wood}} \quad (2)$$

Where HV is the heating value of dry birch wood and m_{wood} is the dry mass of the wood.

Based on the electrical input for wood pulverization (V_G , in kJ), the SEC associated with SSR was expressed as:

$$SEC = \frac{V_G}{Q_A} \quad (3)$$

2.9. Statistical analysis

Oxygen consumption for each treatment was assessed with a minimum of three replicates. Wood dry matter (DM) losses and residual total nitrogen were analyzed using three replicates for samples collected on day 60. Lignocellulosic carbohydrates were measured using pooled samples of three replicates collected on day 60, with each pooled sample subjected to two technical replicates. Statistical analyses were conducted with a confidence level of 95% ($p < 0.05$). All Statistical analyses were conducted using standard descriptive procedures and SigmaPlot 14.0 (Systat Inc., United States). One-way ANOVA followed by a Tukey's HSD Post hoc test was performed to assess statistical differences.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synergistic effects of SSR and PNS on BWO

The performance of BWO was primarily evaluated from two aspects, namely microbial activity and wood degradation. The former is

indicated by the consumption of oxygen and residual TDN. As shown in Fig. 2, three WC groups (WC5, WC10, and WC15) showed insignificant differences among their COCs ($P > 0.05$), but were distinctly less active than the SD group ($P < 0.001$). Regarding oxygen consumption, SD demonstrated a 207% higher COC₈₈ and 262% higher peak OCR than the average values of the three WC groups. These differences may be attributed to the enhanced contact with air caused by larger surface area (Mishra and Yadav, 2022) and increased availability of readily available components (such as soluble or accessible carbohydrate contents) in the sawdust (Tan et al., 2022), which primarily contribute to the peak OCR values (Fan et al., 2020a). Consumption efficiency of TDN was also notably higher in SD than in WC groups. A possible explanation is that SD has smaller particle sizes and a higher pore volume of the substrate pile, which aid in moisture retention, water permeation, and nutrient distribution among particles (Meehnan et al., 2016; Mishra and Yadav, 2022; Zhao et al., 2012). Moreover, there is probably an interplay between oxygen consumption and nitrogen consumption, each influencing the other in a dynamic loop. For instance, high oxygen consumption in SD may be associated with enhanced microbial growth and respiration, which potentially results in faster TDN uptake and wood decomposition (Cen and Xia, 1999). Contrarily, the slow consumption of residual TDN in WC groups leads to excessive accumulation of nitrogen, which can in turn impede the microbial oxygen consumption and wood degradation during BWO (Fan et al., 2020b).

Since BWO is an oxygen-demanding process, its reaction rate can be indicated by OCR. In early-stage BWO (first 14 days), all groups displayed analogous OCR alteration patterns, peaking around day 4–5 and thereafter declining to a lower level (0.03–0.04 mol/kg DM/d). From

day 18–45, PNS significantly improved the OCR of the SD group to 0.17 ± 0.04 mol/kg DM/d ($P < 0.05$), but only slightly influenced those of the WC groups ($P > 0.05$). Moreover, the improvement of SD's OCR through PNS was evident as early as the day following the nutrient supplementation. In contrast, our previous investigation, which used $10 \times 10 \times 5$ mm ash wood blocks, observes that OCR experienced a lag phase of 24 days before showing a significant increase after nutrient re-supplementation (Fan et al., 2020a). While the wood materials used in the previous and current studies may differ in their chemical properties, this comparison still suggests that the smaller particle sizes of sawdust may facilitate the distribution and diffusion of the nutrient solution among particles, making nutrients more accessible to microbes. However, the revitalization of OCR in the SD group became less pronounced after the 3rd nutrient dosage (on day 46) and nearly vanished from day 60 onwards, indicating the presence of other constraints in the later stage of BWO. These constraints may include mass transfer limitations arising from biofilm thickening (Oostra et al., 2001), accumulation of inhibitory metabolites (Graz, 2024), and lowered biodegradability of substrates (Zeng et al., 2016). In summary, these observations imply that the restorative impact of PNS on BWO is intricately linked to the physicochemical properties of the substrate and the regime of nutrient supplementation.

Concerning the degradation of wood, reduction in DM and the removal of carbohydrates (hemicellulose and cellulose) were selected as primary performance indicators, while lignin analysis was omitted due to resource constraints. This selection was based on two considerations: (i) although both hemicellulose and lignin removal present strong predictors of the enzymatic digestibility of lignocellulose (Vidal et al.,

Fig. 2. From top to bottom: cumulative oxygen consumption, oxygen consumption rate, and residual total dissolved nitrogen (TDN) of BWO employing periodic nutrient supplementation and differently sized wood particles. Particle sizes of wood are notes as SD (sawdust), WC5 (5 mm diameter wood cubes), WC10 (10 mm diameter wood cubes), and WC15 (15 mm diameter wood cubes). TDN was assumed to be minorly changed during the testing period from day 14 to day 18. Nutrient supplementation resulted in a 100% increase in residual TDNs on days 18, 32, 46, 60, and 74.

2011), hemicellulose measurement is more straightforward and practical in our case; and (ii) in lignocellulosic composting environments, carbohydrate degradation tends to proceed faster and earlier than lignin degradation (Serramiá et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2017), making it a potentially more sensitive indicator of BWO progress. Fig. 3 depicts the removal of DM and lignocellulosic carbohydrates of wood residues. In terms of DM losses, the differences among the three WC groups were again not significant, and their values were considerably lower than those of the SD group. The highest total DM reduction was observed in SD, as was the removal of carbohydrates (Table S3). Regarding the degradation selectivity for carbohydrates, WC10 and WC15 displayed comparable removal of glucan (the indicator of cellulose) and GAX (the primary hemicellulose polysaccharides of birch wood), similar to reported by Sach et al. that the degrees of fungal attack and cellulose degradation were close between 6- and 19-mm wood chips (Sachs et al., 1991). WC5, however, showed an unexpectedly lower conversion of glucan than WC10 and WC15. This might be attributed to variations in phase contact conditions. As revealed by Fig. 1, a predominant proportion of wood cubes in WC5 was submerged with significantly less surface area exposed to air compared to WC10 and WC15. This reduced contact with air may impose constraints on oxygen transfer, thereby affecting the degradation of cellulose (glucan) (Michelin et al., 2019) and the reaction kinetics (Guardia et al., 2008; Montoya et al., 2021). Furthermore, in the SD group, the degradation of GAX was also higher than that of glucan. Possibly, fine grinding had increased the exposure of hemicelluloses in SD, which are generally easier to degrade enzymatically than cellulose (Horn et al., 2012).

Microbial degradation of lignocellulose is facilitated by extracellular enzymes (Romaní et al., 2006). It is widely accepted that the efficacy of these enzymes relates to the overall specific surface area of the substrate, which is primarily influenced by substrate dimensions and substrate porosity (Zhao et al., 2012). In the current study, variations in particle size of WC yielded marginal differences, whereas changing the particle shape from WC to SD resulted in remarkable improvement. Presumably, the contrasts in specific surface area between different sizes of WC were insufficient for a noticeable effect on enzyme accessibility to be observed, but the differences between SD and WC, resulted from SD's significantly smaller dimensions, larger pore volume of the pile, and increased cracks in individual particles, are much more evident. Moreover, given the limited permeability of fungal hyphae within wood (2–4 mm in depth) (Björndal and Dayton, 2020), the lower thickness may render SD more favourable for fungal colonization and mycelial penetration. According to research on other lignocellulose bioconverting processes such as composting and fermentation (Jiao et al., 2023; Mishra and Yadav, 2022; Sachs et al., 1991), there is normally an optimal range

of particle sizes tailored to specific processes, and the particle size distribution could also influence the aeration condition, porosity, nitrogen content, and bacterial diversity during the composting of green waste (Reyes-Torres et al., 2018). In this study, only one single size of sawdust was screened and investigated in small-scale batch BWO reactors, leaving questions to be explored in large-scale applications. For instance, wood shredding typically produces sawdust with varied size distributions, yet how this size heterogeneity affects mass transfer and degradation in larger BWO systems is not well understood. Moreover, smaller-sized wood particles, due to their lower physical strength, may cause significant substrate compaction in larger volumes, leading to the formation of dead zones and mass transfer limitations within the pile (Orthodoxou et al., 2015). Therefore, the advantages of sawdust over wood cubes demonstrated in this study may not necessarily be generalized to larger-scale setups, and future research could investigate the optimization of particle sizing and the effect of substrate size distribution for scaled-up BWO systems.

3.2. Effect of nutrient sources and PNS on sawdust BWO

In our previous study in 2020, two distinct combinations of nutrient sources and wood block sizes were tested: artificial nutrient medium paired with larger wood blocks (10 × 10 × 10 mm), and fresh human urine paired with smaller wood blocks (10 × 10 × 5 mm) (Fan et al., 2020a, 2020b). Higher performance was noted in the latter combination, which could now be ascribed to the differences in nutrient sources, given the marginal variation between WC groups observed in Section 3.1. To verify this speculation and explore further enhancements of BWO, the experiment in this section investigated the performance of SD-BWO systems with PNS of HU and SM respectively. A control group receiving HU only once at the beginning was also set up to validate the individual impact of PNS. As shown in Fig. 4, the COC of SD-HU-PNS was 1.53 times and 1.81 times higher than those of SD-SM-PNS and SD-HU, confirming the positive effect of human urine and PNS respectively ($P < 0.05$). The promotion of OCR by PNS was reproduced in both groups receiving PNS, while SD-HU-PNS exhibited a larger relative increase in OCR compared to SD-SM-PNS ($P < 0.001$). The TDN consumption for all three groups was rapid, with over 98.5% being depleted within the initial 14 days. Afterwards, the two treatment groups receiving PNS exhibited highly comparable TDN consumption rates.

Since the total nitrogen inputs from HU and SM were identical, and their consumption patterns of TDN were comparable, it can be inferred that the different effectiveness between the two nutrient sources lie in other aspects. From Table 2, three primary distinctions can be identified between HU and SM: (1) variations in nitrogen forms, with urea

Fig. 3. Removal of dry mass (left) and carbohydrate contents (right) of the wood material over 88-day incubation. Particle sizes of wood are notes as SD (sawdust), WC5 (5 mm diameter wood cubes), WC10 (10 mm diameter wood cubes), and WC15 (15 mm diameter wood cubes). Due to the presence of fungal biomass in the wood after BWO treatments, dry mass losses and glucan removals were slightly underestimated.

Fig. 4. From top to bottom: cumulative oxygen consumption, oxygen consumption rate, and residual total dissolved nitrogen (TDN) of sawdust-sized BWO with different nutrient supplementation regimes. Abbreviations are as follows: SD (sawdust), HU (human urine), SM (synthetic medium), PNS (periodic nutrient supplementation). The residual TDN in SD-HU was measured only on day 60 and equals to 0.15%. For SD-HU-PNS and SD-SM-PNS, TDNs were assumed to be minorly changed from day 14 to day 18, and nutrient supplementation resulted in a 100% increase in residual TDNs on days 18, 32, and 46.

dominating in HU and ammonia nitrogen in SM; (2) differences in buffering agents, as HU employs bicarbonate ions derived from urea hydrolysis, whereas SM was prepared with phosphate-buffered saline (and consequently contained higher concentrations of sodium and potassium ions); (3) the complexity of compositions, as HU encompasses a greater variety of trace elements and larger amount of organic matters (OMs, indicated by COD). If OMs serve solely as carbon sources, they can

be degraded by BWO microbes and result in an increase in OCR. However, the COD of supplemented HU was merely 0.021 mol O₂/kg DM, significantly lower than the maximum OCR elevation after each supplementation (0.20–0.34 mol O₂/kg DM). Therefore, the high efficacy of HU is likely attributed to other factors, such as potential pH-regulating and metabolic-enhancing effects caused by urea hydrolysis, higher bioavailability of certain nutrients, low salinity, or OMs functioning as

Fig. 5. Removal of dry mass (left) and carbohydrate contents (right) of the wood material over 60-day incubation. Abbreviations are as follows: SD (sawdust), HU (human urine), SM (synthetic medium), PNS (periodic nutrient supplementation). Due to the presence of fungal biomass in the wood after BWO treatments, dry mass losses and glucan removals were slightly underestimated.

biostimulants (Orwin et al., 2010). Further investigation is required to elucidate HU's unique physicochemical properties and the mechanisms of its efficacy on BWO.

Fig. 5 shows the patterns of wood degradation, which were well aligned with that of COC. After 60 days of incubation, the DM loss of SD-HU-PNS amounted to 34.2%, which was 1.6 times and 2.0 times higher than that of SD-SM-PNS and SD-HU. Remarkably, this value established a new record for DM loss compared to all our prior investigations. The degradation of carbohydrates was 26.0% for SD-HU, 29.7% for SD-SM-PNS, and 45.5% for SD-HU-PNS. SD-HU exhibited a higher selectivity towards glucan degradation, while in the other two groups, the removal of GAX and glucan were comparable. It is noteworthy that SD-SM-PNS did not exhibit significant degradation selectivity for GAX over glucan on day 60, whereas such selectivity was evident on day 88 in the experiment detailed in Section 3.1. Despite the variations in the wood materials and inoculum used between the two sets of experiments, this difference may indicate limitations in cellulose degradation during the later stages (60–88 days) of BWO, hence the hemicellulose degradation prevailed. Nevertheless, since carbohydrate analysis was performed only at the end of the experiments, the dynamic changes in carbohydrate fractions during different phases of degradation remain unclear. Moreover, the discrepancy between total DM loss and the DM loss estimated from total carbohydrate removal (34.2% vs. 24.4%, in the case of SD-HU-PNS) suggests that other wood components, presumably lignin, were also removed during BWO. However, the lack of lignin analysis limits our knowledge about the evolution of lignin and the impact of SSR on lignin removal within the BWO system. Future research should incorporate lignin analysis and (semi-)continuous compositional monitoring of substrates to gain deeper insights into these aspects, which are crucial for understanding process dynamics and identifying potential limitations.

3.3. Energy efficacy of SSR to improve the heat production potential of BWO

Grinding wood has the potential to boost BWO, but it results in increased electrical input, especially for finer particle sizes. To evaluate the energy performance of BWO with different particle sizes, eight energy parameters were assessed for WC5, WC10, WC15, SD, and SD-HU-PNS, based on their average OCR values over the first 46 days (Table S4). Fig. 6 illustrates the thermal efficiency (TE) and specific energy consumption (SEC) of selected BWO groups. Similar to the trends observed for COC and DM losses, SD-HU-PNS presented the highest TE (39.8%),

Fig. 6. Estimated thermal efficiency and specific energy consumption of selected BWO treatments. Treatments of SD (sawdust), WC5 (5 mm diameter wood cubes), WC10 (10 mm diameter wood cubes), and WC15 (15 mm diameter wood cubes) received periodic supplementation of synthetic medium. SD-HU-PNS, which used sawdust-sized wood, received periodic supplementation of human urine.

followed by SD (19.8%), WC10 (6.1%), WC5 (5.7%), and WC15 (5.3%). Among the three WC groups that exhibited comparable TE values, the SEC declined as particle size increased, with WC15 ranking the lowest (3.2%) and WC5 being the highest (9.2%). In contrast, the two SD groups, despite having even higher energy input, achieved increased energy production, consequently leading to reduced SEC values (8.3% for SD and 4.1% for SD-HU-PNS). Calculations revealed that processing 1000 kg of DM wood from WC to SD consumes 55–72 kWh of electricity, yet generates potentially an additional 680.6–719.5 kWh of useful heat output, yielding a return on investment exceeding 1000%. Therefore, fine grinding of wood can be considered economically viable (in terms of electricity costs) to improve the performance of BWO. Furthermore, sawdust is often deemed a low-value forestry by-product facing challenges in its thermochemical utilization as fuel, due to its low calorific value, low energy density, high volatility, and high particularity (Emenike et al., 2023). Our investigation implies that using readily available sawdust residue as a feedstock for BWO can enhance both reaction performance and energy efficiency, presenting a new perspective on energy-dedicated sawdust valorization.

The energy evaluation in this study has several limitations. Firstly, the theoretical heat generation of BWO (Q_{bio}) was estimated based on oxygen consumption, which introduces inherent inaccuracies (Fan et al., 2021). Secondly, the oxygen consumption data used for calculation were derived from small-scale BWO tests, which may not reflect the situation in real-scale systems. Thirdly, the calculated useful heat output (Q_A) may be inaccurate due to simplifications and assumptions made in the heat transfer model. Finally, yet importantly, not all this Q_A can be recovered for end use. Some of the heat may be retained in the pile to maintain a proper temperature for sustained biological activity, and additional heat losses will occur during the heat recovery and transportation processes (Smith et al., 2017). The accurate modelling of heat dynamics in large-scale BWO systems would require more realistic operational data and a more comprehensive process model, as demonstrated elsewhere (Sessa and Bhandari, 2023; Walther et al., 2017).

3.4. General discussion and implications

In general, SSR can improve the conversion efficiency of lignocellulosic materials through two main mechanisms: (i) by altering the physical properties of the material, such as increasing the specific surface area and decreasing crystallinity, and (ii) by affecting heat and mass transfer, which can further influence operational parameters like temperature, moisture, and oxygen availability. For both thermochemical (Kumar et al., 2020) and enzymatic (Vidal et al., 2011) lignocellulosic conversions, SSR appears effective only within a critical particle size range: reducing particle sizes beyond this range, whether larger or smaller, may lead to minimal enhancement in conversion efficiency. According to this study, the upper effective limit of SSR for enhancing BWO should be below 5 mm. However, most green waste composting studies have used larger particle sizes (typically above 10 mm) (Reyes-Torres et al., 2018), and particle sizes smaller than 15 mm have even been reported to hinder in-pile oxygen diffusion and negatively affect final compost quality (Mishra and Yadav, 2022). Several factors may influence the optimal particle sizing for composting-like systems: (i) feedstock properties, specifically the physicochemical differences between woody and herbaceous lignocellulose and their relative proportions within the substrate matrix. Substrates with higher woody lignocellulose content may necessitate smaller particle sizes to enhance surface area and accessibility; (ii) system design, including factors such as geometric dimensions, substrate mixing, and aeration regime. In reactors with larger volumes and challenging inter-particle mass transfer, larger particle sizes may be advantageous in preventing compaction and improving the overall performances; and (iii) the physiological characteristics of microbial agents, which may involve different degradative mechanisms and therefore have varying requirements for the optimal particle size of lignocellulosic materials. All these aspects should be

considered when determining the feedstock size for an efficient lignocellulosic bioconversion process.

To ensure the economic feasibility of lignocellulosic conversion at an industrial scale, particle size determination should also consider various operational and economic factors, including energy and equipment costs, handling and transportation, and downstream processing. In this study, the maximum DM loss of wood achieved was 34.2% after 60 days. Further improvements in the extent and rate of degradation may bring BWO closer to economic viability, but this is unlikely to be achieved solely through SSR, as it presents a high-energy pretreatment and does not address the inherent chemical recalcitrance of lignin and lignin-carbohydrate complexes (Barakat et al., 2014). While physical size reduction could only improve the conversion efficiency to approximately 50%, chemical pretreatment, regardless of particle size, can achieve a conversion efficiency of up to 70% (Vidal et al., 2011). Therefore, the combination of mechanical SSR with low-energy and non/low-toxic chemical treatments, such as solvent treatment with polar aprotic solvents, ionic liquids, and deep eutectic solvents, may have a potential to further improve the degradation efficiency and energy efficacy of BWO (Yin et al., 2021).

4. Conclusion

The present study investigated the impact of substrate size reduction and periodic nutrient supplementation on lab-scale biological wood oxidation (BWO). Insignificant differences were observed among BWO treatments using differently sized wood cubes (5, 10, and 15 mm), whereas BWO using sawdust demonstrated a notably higher performance, indicated by cumulative oxygen consumption, nitrogen uptake efficiency, carbohydrate removal, and dry mass loss of wood. Periodic nutrient supplementation effectively resumed the oxygen consumption rate of sawdust-BWO within the first 60 days, and human urine exhibited higher effectiveness as a nutrient source than synthetic medium. The combination of sawdust, periodic nutrient supplementation, and human urine gave the highest cumulative oxygen consumption and dry mass loss (34.2% after 60 days). However, the promotional effect of periodic nutrient supplementation became less pronounced after day 60, suggesting the presence of limiting factors other than nutrient availability in the later BWO stages. Fine grinding of wood cubes into sawdust can yield up to 10 times more heat output than the electricity input it requires, thereby presenting an energy-efficient means to enhance BWO. Further research should critically investigate the optimal particle sizing for upscaled BWO, decomposition phases of BWO and corresponding changes in lignocellulosic fractions, human urine's composition and its effectiveness, and limitations beyond nutrient availability for long-running BWO.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anran Li: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Virginia Natonek:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gijs van Erven:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Cees J.N. Buisman:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Wei-Shan Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.123012>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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